

IKKINCHI TARTIBLI INTEGRO-DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMA UCHUN TO'G'RI VA TESKARI MASALALAR

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu ishda ikkinchi tartibli integro-differensial tenglama uchun bir teskari masala bayon qilingan va tadqiq etilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *ikkinchi tartibli integro-differensial tenglama, Riman-Liuvill ma'nosidagi kasr tartibli integral, teskari masala.*

ПРЯМАЯ И ОБРАТНАЯ ЗАДАЧИ ДЛЯ ИНТЕГРО-ДИФФЕРЕНЦИАЛЬНОГО УРАВНЕНИЯ ВТОРОГО ПОРЯДКА

Аннотация: *В этой работе была сформулирована и исследована обратная задача для интегро-дифференциального уравнения второго порядка.*

Ключевые слова: *Интегро-дифференциальное уравнение второго порядка, Интеграл Римана-Лювилля в смысле дроби, обратная задача.*

DIRECT AND INVERSE PROBLEMS FOR AN INTEGRO-DIFFERENTIAL EQUATION OF THE SECOND ORDER

Annotation: *In this paper, the inverse problem for a second order integro-differential equation was formulated and investigated.*

Keywords: *Integro-differential equation of the second order, Riemann-Liouville integral in the sense of (fractions), inverse problem.*

I Kirish. So'ngi vaqtlarda noma'lum manbali differensial tenglamalar bilan shug'illanishga bo'lgan qiziqish ortib bormoqda. Bunga sabab ko'plab issiqlik taqalish va diffuziya jarayonlarini matematik modelini tuzish noma'lum manbali differensial tenglama uchun qo'yiladigan masalalarga keltiriladi. Bunday differensial tenglamalar uchun teskari masalalar ko'plab tadqiqotchilar tomonidan o'rganilgan (masalan, ushbu [1]–[10] ishlarga qaralsin).

II Masalani qo'yilishi.

(0, 1) oraliqda ushbu

$$y''(x) - \lambda I_{0x}^{\alpha} y(x) = f(x) \quad (1)$$

ikkinchi tartibli integro-differensial tenglamani qaraylik, bu yerda $y(x)$ – noma'lum funksiya; $f(x)$ – berilgan uzluksiz funksiya; λ, γ - o'zgarmas haqiqiy sonlar bo'lib; $I_{0x}^{\gamma} y(x)$ - Riman-Liuvill ma'nosida γ (kasr) tartibli integral [11]

$$I_{0x}^{\gamma} y(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\gamma)} \int_0^x (x-t)^{\gamma-1} y(t) dt.$$

Koshi masalasi. Shunday $y(x)$ funksiya topilsinki, u quyidagi xossalarga ega bo'lsin:

1) $(0, 1)$ oraliqda (1) tenglamani qanoatlantirsin;

2) $C^1[0,1]$ $C^2(0,1)$ sinfga tegishli bo'lsin;

3) $x=0$ nuqtada esa

$$y(0) = A_1, \quad y'(0) = A_2, \quad (2)$$

chegaraviy shartlarni qanoatlantirsin, bu yerda A_1, A_2 – berilgan o'zgarmas haqiqiy sonlar.

(1) tenglamani ketma-ket 2 marta integrallab, (2) shartdan foydalanib,

$$y(x) - \frac{\lambda}{\Gamma(\gamma+2)} \int_0^x (x-t)^{\gamma+2-1} y(t) dt = A_1 + A_2 x + \int_0^x (x-z) f(z) dz \quad (3)$$

ko'rinishdagi integral tenglamani hosil qilamiz.

(3) da ba'zi belgilashlarni kiritib, uni ko'rinishda yozib olamiz, bu yerda

$$g(x) = A_1 + A_2 x + \int_0^x (x-z) f(z) dz, \quad \beta = \gamma + 2, \quad K(x,t) = \frac{(x-t)^{\beta-1}}{\Gamma(\beta)}$$

$$y(x) - \lambda \int_a^x K(x,t) y(t) dt = g(x) \quad (4)$$

(4) Volltera ikkinchi tur tenglamasi bo'lib, uni ketma-ket yaqinlashish usuli yordamida yechamiz.

$$K_1(x,t) = \frac{(x-t)^{\beta-1}}{\Gamma(\beta)} \quad \text{va} \quad K_i(x,y) = \int_y^x K_1(x,t) K_{i-1}(t,y) dt$$

rekurent formuladan foydalanib, ba'zi hisoblashlarni amalga oshirib

$$K_n(x,t) = \frac{(x-t)^{n\beta-1}}{\Gamma(n\beta)}, \quad n=1,2,3,\dots \text{ topamiz.}$$

Integral tenglamalar nazariyasiga ko'ra, (4) tenglamaning yechimi

$$y(x) = g(x) + \lambda \int_a^x R(x,t, \lambda) g(t) dt \quad (5)$$

ko'rinishda yozib olamiz, bu yerda

$$R(x,t, \lambda) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lambda^{n-1} K_n(x,t), \quad R(x,t, \lambda) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda^{n-1} (x-t)^{\beta n-1}}{\Gamma(\beta n)}$$

(5) da $g(x) = A_1 + A_2x + \int_0^x (x-z)f(z)dz$ ekanligi e'tiborga olib, ba'zi

soddalastirishlarni amalga oshirib Koshi masalasining yechimini

$$y(x) = A_1 E_{\beta,1}(\lambda x^\beta) + A_2 x E_{\beta,2}(\lambda x^\beta) + \int_0^x (x-z) E_{\beta,4}[\lambda(x-z)^\beta] f(z) dz \quad (6)$$

ko'rinishda topamiz, bu yerda $E_{\alpha,\beta}(z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^n}{\Gamma(\alpha n + \beta)}$ - Mittag-Leffler funksiyasi

[12].

Endi

$$y''(x) - \lambda I_{0x}^\gamma y(x) = kf(x) \quad (7)$$

tenglamani (0,1) oraliqda qaraylik, bu yerda $y(x)$ -noma'lum funksiya, λ, γ - o'zgarmas haqiqiy sonlar, $f(x)$ -berilgan funksiya, k -noma'lum son.

T₁ masala Shunday $y(x)$ -funksiya va k sonni topilsinki u quyidagi xossalarga ega bo'lsin:

1) (0, 1) oraliqda (7) tenglamani qanoatlantirsin;

2) $C^1[0,1]$ I $C^2(0,1)$ sinfga tegishli bo'lsin;

3) $x=0$, $x=1$ nuqtalarda esa

$$y(0) = A_1, \quad y(1) = B_1 \quad (8)$$

$$y(\xi_0) = D_1 \quad (9)$$

shartlarni qanoatlantirsin, bu yerda A_1, B_1, D_1 - berilgan o'zgarmas haqiqiy sonlar.

T₁ masala yechimini (6) formuladan foydalanib,

$$y(x) = A_1 E_{\beta,1}(\lambda x^\beta) + A_2 x E_{\beta,2}(\lambda x^\beta) + k \int_0^x (x-z) E_{\beta,4}[\lambda(x-z)^\beta] f(z) dz \quad (10)$$

ko'rinishda yozib olamiz, bu yerda A_2 noma'lum son.

(10) tenglikda $y(1) = B_1$ shartdan foydalanib, noma'lum A_2 ni

$$A_2 = \frac{B_1 - A_1 E_{\beta,1}(\lambda) - k \int_0^1 (1-z) E_{\beta,4}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz}{E_{\beta,2}(\lambda)} \quad (11)$$

ko'rinishda topamiz.

Endi, $y(\xi_0) = D_1$ nolokal shartdan k ni

$$k = \frac{A_1 E_{\beta,1}(\lambda \xi_0^\beta) + \frac{B_1 - A_1 E_{\beta,1}(\lambda)}{E_{\beta,2}(\lambda)} \xi_0 E_{\beta,2}(\lambda \xi_0^\beta) - D_1}{\xi_0 E_{\beta,2}(\lambda \xi_0^\beta) - \frac{\int_0^1 (1-z) E_{\beta,4}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz}{E_{\beta,2}(\lambda)} - \int_0^{\xi_0} (\xi_0 - z) E_{\beta,4}[\lambda(\xi_0 - z)^\beta] f(z) dz} \quad (12)$$

ko'rinishda topamiz.

(11) va (12) larni (10) ga qo'yib, T_1 masalaning yechimi hosil qilamiz.

1-teorema. Agar

$$\xi_0 E_{\beta,2}(\lambda \xi_0^\beta) \int_0^1 (1-z) E_{\beta,2}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz \neq \int_0^{\xi_0} (\xi_0 - z) E_{\beta,2}[\lambda(\xi_0 - z)^\beta] f(z) dz$$

bo'lsa, u holda T_1 masala yagona yechimga ega bo'ladi.

T_2 masala (7) tenglamada shunday $y(x)$ -funksiya va k sonni topilsinki u quyidagi xossalarga ega bo'lsin:

1) $(0, 1)$ oraliqda (7) tenglamani qanoatlantirsin;

2) $C^1[0,1]$ I $C^2(0,1)$ sinfga tegishli bo'lsin;

3) $x=0, x=1$ nuqtalarda esa

$$y'(0) = A_2, \quad y(1) = B_1 \tag{13}$$

va (9) shartlarni qanoatlantirsin, bu yerda A_2, B_1, D_1 - berilgan o'zgarmas haqiqiy sonlar.

T_2 masala yechimini (6) formuladan foydalanib,

$$y(x) = A_1 E_{\beta,1}(\lambda x^\beta) + A_2 x E_{\beta,2}(\lambda x^\beta) + k \int_0^x (x-z) E_{\beta,4}[\lambda(x-z)^\beta] f(z) dz \tag{14}$$

ko'rinishida yozib olamiz, bu yerda A_1 noma'lum son

(12) formulada $y(1) = B_1$ shartdan foydalanib, noma'lum A_1 ni

$$A_1 = \frac{B_1 - A_2 E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - k \int_0^1 (1-z) E_{\beta,2}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz}{E_{\beta,1}(\lambda)} \tag{15}$$

ko'rinishda topamiz.

Endi, $y(\xi_0) = D_1$ nolokal shartdan k ni

$$k = \frac{A_2 \xi_0 E_{\beta,2}(\lambda \xi_0^\beta) + \frac{B_1 - A_2 E_{\beta,2}(\lambda)}{E_{\beta,1}(\lambda)} E_{\beta,1}(\lambda \xi_0^\beta) - D_1}{\int_0^1 (1-z) E_{\beta,2}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz - \int_0^{\xi_0} (\xi_0 - z) E_{\beta,2}[\lambda(\xi_0 - z)^\beta] f(z) dz} \tag{16}$$

ko'rinishda topamiz.

(15) va (16) larni (14) ga qo'yib, T_2 masalaning yechimi hosil qilamiz.

2-teorema. Agar

$$E_{\beta,1}(\lambda \xi_0^\beta) \int_0^1 (1-z) E_{\beta,2}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz \neq \int_0^{\xi_0} (\xi_0 - z) E_{\beta,2}[\lambda(\xi_0 - z)^\beta] f(z) dz$$

bo'lsa, u holda T_2 masala yagona yechimga ega bo'ladi.

T_3 masala (7) tenglamada shunday $y(x)$ -funksiya va k sonni topilsinki u quyidagi xossalarga ega bo'lsin:

- 1) $(0, 1)$ oraliqda (7) tenglamani qanoatlantirsin;
 - 2) $C^1[0,1]$ I $C^2(0,1)$ sinfga tegishli bo'lsin;
 - 3) $x=0, x=1$ nuqtalarda esa
- $$y(0) = A_1, y'(1) = B_2 \quad (17)$$

va (9) shartlarni qanoatlantirsin, bu yerda A_1, B_2, D_1 - berilgan o'zgarmas haqiqiy sonlar.

T_3 masala yechimini (6) formuladan foydalanib,

$$y(x) = A_1 E_{\beta,1}(\lambda x^\beta) + A_2 x E_{\beta,2}(\lambda x^\beta) + k \int_0^x (x-z) E_{\beta,4}[\lambda(x-z)^\beta] f(z) dz \quad (18)$$

yoziq olamiz, bu yerda A_2 noma'lum son.

(17) tenglikda $y'(1) = B_2$ shartdan foydalanib, noma'lum A_2 ni

$$A_2 = \frac{B_2 - A_1 E_{\beta,\beta}(\lambda) - k \int_0^1 E_{\beta,1}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz}{E_{\beta,1}(\lambda)} \quad (19)$$

ko'rinishda topamiz.

Endi, $y(\xi_0) = D_1$ nolokal shartdan k ni

$$k = \frac{A_1 E_{\beta,1}(\lambda \xi_0^\beta) + \xi_0 E_{\beta,1}(\lambda \xi_0^\beta) \left[\frac{B_2 - A_1 E_{\beta,\beta}(\lambda)}{E_{\beta,1}(\lambda)} \right] - D_1}{\xi_0 E_{\beta,2}(\lambda \xi_0^\beta) \frac{\int_0^1 E_{\beta,1}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz}{E_{\beta,1}(\lambda)} - \int_0^{\xi_0} (\xi_0 - z) E_{\beta,2}[\lambda(\xi_0 - z)^\beta] f(z) dz} \quad (20)$$

ko'rinishda topamiz.

(19) va (20) larni (18) ga qo'yib, T_3 masalaning yechimi hosil qilamiz.

3-teorema. Agar

$$\xi_0 E_{\beta,2}(\lambda \xi_0^\beta) \frac{\int_0^1 E_{\beta,1}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz}{E_{\beta,1}(\lambda)} \neq \int_0^{\xi_0} (\xi_0 - z) E_{\beta,2}[\lambda(\xi_0 - z)^\beta] f(z) dz$$

bo'lsa, u holda T_3 masala yagona yechimga ega bo'ladi.

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